

Review Article

A History of the Federal Road Safety Corps, 1988-2016

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Abstract

That safety on the roads is a sine qua non to national development is no longer in doubt. Without this, multiple accidents and of course the concomitant carnage and death of nationals who would have contributed to national development would be the order of the day. The Federal Government of Nigeria thus decided to establish an arm to ensure safety on roads. This paper examined the history of the Federal Roads Safety Corps (F.R.S.C.) of Nigeria between 1988 and 2016. The paper employed the use and synthesis of available materials on the subject. It was found out that though the F.R.S.C. was doing its best to ensure safety on the roads, more still had to be done in this regard. It was therefore recommended that the Federal Government and States should further empower the safety organizations to achieve the objectives of their founding fathers.

Keywords: Roads, Safety, Corps, Commission, Nigeria and National development.

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Introduction

A study of the history of the Federal Road Safety Commission requires a look at the antecedents of road safety generally. This is because Nigeria's experience at having macadamized roads is less than two centuries. As no nation is an island unto itself, taking a look at antecedents of road safety elsewhere would shed light and give a clearer understanding of the Nigerian experience. One more point to make at this early stage is that the triple concepts of roads, safety and vehicles are quite interwoven. One would not talk of roads without safety or roads without vehicles and

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vice versa. It is, therefore, in the light of the foregoing that the three shall be taken as one at least for the purpose of this paper.

Be that as it may, it would be interesting at point out that roads preceded the introduction of wheels and even motor vehicles. Steve (2016) submits that thousands of years before the advent of motor vehicles or wheels and even urban planning, roads had been in existence. The necessity to procure food and water made humans to walk the same path for years and with the invention of trading activities, some of these paths were transformed into trade routes which later became a huge network crossing political boundaries and even continents as readily exemplified by the Trans-Saharan trade of pre-colonial Africa.

Steve (2016) further opines that the introduction of wheels some 7,000 years ago brought new demands on the paths and routes usually used by humans. The paths and routes were no longer passable at all times of the year. The nature of the wheels, with its heavy loads turned the paths and routes into muddy areas especially during the raining seasons. This had made transportation either slow or out rightly impossible at such times.

The foregoing partly explains why India and Mesopotamia devised means of making paved roads as early as 4,000 B.C (Steve, 2016). These were soon followed by the Romans who wanted faster and easier means of transporting their troops to further deepen their colonial ambitions.

The modern roads, however, had their origins in the invention of a Scottish, John M.C Adam, who in the early 19th century introduced modern road construction techniques. Subsequent road construction methods had improved M.C Adam's invention to suit the vehicles which were introduced in the 20th century (Steve, 2016). Indeed, the American interstate and the German *autobahn* were constructed with the same purpose as the Romans namely; to move troops. These, however, were to pay off for civilians' use especially after the cessation of hostilities occasioned by the two world wars.

Bellis (2016), while discussing on the subject, notes that modern day roads could directly be linked to the employment of asphalt blocks in Paris in 1824 and by 1872; an improved version of asphalt had been used in New York, the United States of America (U.S.A.).

Nigeria, like other nations of the world, was not also left out of developing her intricate web of transportation system which included humans and beasts of burden like cattle, donkey and horse. This also led to the stimulation and growth of paths and routes which served not only internal purpose but were part of the international trade of Africa at the time.

Ighodalo (2009) notes that the first road in Nigeria was constructed by Lord Lugard in 1904 which linked Zaria to Zungeru. This road, it must be noted, was only a mule road and it was later extended to Sokoto, Katsina and Maiduguri. The first motorable road in Nigeria was from Ibadan to Oyo which was constructed in 1906. At independence in 1960, most of the roads in Nigeria

were narrow and winding because they were meant principally to be feeder roads to connect the various parts of the interior of Nigeria to collect agricultural produce and also to facilitate the entrenchment of colonial administration (Ighodalo, 2009). These roads were thus neither aimed at achieving integration among the peoples of Nigeria or foster and engender national development.

Ighodalo (2009) further submits that roads in Nigeria as at independence were classified into Trunks 'A', 'B' and 'C' owned and maintained by the federal, state and local governments respectively while Trunk 'F' roads were formally under the control of states but were taken over by the Federal Government. The above categories are, however, not sacrosanct as economic realities of the day had made the Federal Government to allow states to rehabilitate roads in their domain with a plan of re-imbursement at a later period.

That vehicles had come to play significant roles in the history of Nigeria cannot be over-emphasized. Such was the case that the nation had come up to with a National Automotive Industry Policy (Adejumo, 2015). BBC (2016) submits that Nigeria had seen her first car by the turn of the 20th century and before the first quarter of the century had ended, Nigeria was already importing cars from Europe. This had definitely increased the use of available roads and had also introduced new challenges in the area of safety on the roads.

Safety on the roads has been as old as the introduction of motor vehicles. People leave the comfort of their homes to pursue their various interests. At the back of each traveler is the hope of returning home safely. Circumstances, most often than not, always proved otherwise and thus making this impossible. So many people had thus met untimely death or had become incapacitated due to injuries sustained through motor accidents. The dimension that this had taken had drawn the attention of governments and international organizations to the potential and real dangers posed by the dangers on the roads. To buttress the foregoing point, in 2016 alone, the United Nations Organization (U.N.O.) had warned that about thirteen million people will die as a result of motor accidents or that there would be three thousand deaths each day from the same problem. It was further observed that between twenty and fifty million people will sustain non-fatal injuries arising from motor accidents this year alone (International Road Federation, 2016).

The foregoing figures are staggering and alarming indeed. Little wonder, therefore, that the Nigerian governments over the years had taken pro-active measures to nib this monster in the bud. These efforts on the part of successive Nigerian governments to ensure safety on the roads shall be the next focus of this paper.

The formative years

Balogun (2016) submits that the nation had no coordinated attempt at ensuring safety on the roads until 1988 when the Federal Military Government of Nigeria under General Ibrahim Babangida enacted a decree establishing the F.R.S.C.

Prior to this time, the Shell Petroleum Development Company (S.P.D.C.) and the Nigeria Army started the initiative of introducing official road safety measures in Nigeria between 1960 and 1972. These efforts culminated in the launching of the annual Road Safety Week by the Army in 1972 (Balogun, 2016). Oyo State under the leadership of chief Bola Ige took up the gauntlet in 1977 when it introduced the Oyo State Road Safety Corps. Though this was preceded in 1974, when the Federal Government of General Yakubu Gowon established the National Road Safety Commission, all these efforts were not sustained. It must be admitted that the efforts in Oyo State aimed at improving safety on the roads yielded improvements and remarkable achievements were recorded in limiting the excesses of road users thereby reducing the carnage on the roads at the time.

But as it was stated previously, the attempt by the Federal Government was not faithfully implemented and it soon fizzled out. In Oyo State, most of the achievements recorded were at best restricted to local roads and were limited within the boundaries of the state. To compound issues, in 1983, the Federal Government of Alhaji Shehu Shagari, for reasons that are still not clear other than petty partisan politics, restricted the activities of the Oyo State Road Safety Corps to Trunk 'B' and 'C' roads. This blow dealt to the efforts of the Oyo State Government led to the demise of the corps. Thus it were, that for five years, there were no concerted efforts on the part of any Nigerian government to ensure safety on the roads and therefore road users were left to their devices with the resultant increase in death on the roads. This was the situation in 1988 when the F.R.S.C. was established.

The Growth of F.R.S.C.

Federal Road Safety Corps (2016a) submits that the Federal Government promulgated Decree number 45 of 1988 establishing the F.R.S.C. This decree was amended in 1992 through the Decree 35 which was further amended by the National Assembly known as the F.R.S.C. Act cap 141 laws of the Federation of Nigeria. These had provided the legal framework for the activities of the F.R.S.C.

As at 2010, the F.R.S.C. was divided into twelve zones, thirty-seven sectors, one hundred and sixty-four units and one hundred and thirty-eight information processing centres (Chidoka, 2010). Chidoka (2010) further opines that the F.R.S.C. maintains its presence in all the states of the federation and has its Headquarters in Abuja.

In order to enhance its performance and deliver on its mandate of ensuring safety on the roads, the F.R.S.C. is employing the use of information technology. This is buttressed by the fact that two hundred and sixty-three of its formations had been linked with Vsat (Chidoka, 2010).

That the F.R.S.C. had grown from its humble beginnings in 1988 is also illustrated by the fact that it had witnessed remarkable growth in the size of its personnel. Chidoka (2010), shedding more light on this, submits that as at 2010, the Commission had a staff strength of twenty - eight thousand. A breakdown of this reveals that thirteen thousand were permanent staff while fifteen thousand were special marshals engaged by the Commission to achieve its mandate. In addition to the above, the Commission had an ad hoc staff of twelve thousand which were drawn from members of the National Youth Service Corps (N.Y.S.C.) and secondary schools.

Another remarkable feat achieved by the F.R.S.C. in the area of growth was the establishment of its own training school known as the F.R.S.C. Academic and Training School. Between 2007 and 2010, the school had successfully trained forty-two staff of the Commission (Chidoka, 2010). The training and re-training of staff is indeed a laudable achievement as members of staff were afforded the rare opportunity of updating their knowledge and skills. This no doubt, had contributed to the effectiveness of the Commission. As a corollary to the foregoing point, the World Bank had also assisted the Commission in the area of staff development.

Before leaving this section, it is quite pertinent to note that the F.R.S.C had constructed its own housing schemes for staff, built Micro Finance Bank and had also successfully implemented the e-payment policy of the Federal Government (Chidoka 2010). All these are pointers to the fact that the F.R.S.C had not been stagnant since its inception in 1988. It had indeed witnessed vertical growth as had been aptly demonstrated. It is one thing to witness vertical growth while it is another thing entirely to translate such a growth into meaningful development. The next focus of this paper, therefore, is to examine the contributions of the F.R.S.C to national development.

Contributions of F.R.S.C to National Development

In order to effectively assess the contributions of the F.R.S.C to National development, it would be quite pertinent to understand the mandate of the Commission. In the first instance, it would provide the much needed framework to examine the activities of the Commission. Secondly, it would also afford the opportunity for determining whether the aims and objectives of the founding fathers of the Commission have been achieved or not. Federal Road Safety Corps (2016b) noted that the Commission was, *inter-alia* established to make the highways safe for motorists and other road users. It was also to recommend works and devices designed to eliminate or minimize accidents on all highways with a view to minimizing accidents on such roads. Its mandate also includes the education of motorists and other road users on the necessity of maintaining discipline and self-control on the highways. Furthermore, the F.R.S.C was saddled

with the onerous task of eradicating or at best eliminating accidents on the highways. It was also expected to clear obstructions on highways to prevent further mishaps.

Moreover, the F.R.S.C. was established to design and produce vehicle license to drivers. This was done to ensure that only certified and trusted personnel would be at the wheels at all times. In addition, the issuance of vehicle number plates comes under the purview of the F.R.S.C. This is very pertinent when one considers the security implications of the issuance of number plates.

Coupled with the above, the F.R.S.C. had been mandated to harmonize highway codes and improve upon them as necessary. The care of accident victims and the regulation of arbitrary use of sirens are part of the responsibilities of the F.R.S.C.

Federal Road Safety Commission Corps (2016c) further opines that the F.R.S.C. was also saddled with the responsibility of regulating the use of mobile phones, safety belts and motorcycles on highways.

Finally, the F.R.S.C. was expected to cooperate and collaborate with other relevant agencies to ensure safety on the roads (Federal Road Safety Corps (2016c). The foregoing recognizes the fact that maintaining safety on the highways and indeed on all roads could be very daunting indeed hence the need for synergy among relevant agencies.

To say the least, one would be readily argue that the task before the F.R.S.C. is not a mean one indeed. Since inception, the Commission had recorded notable feats in keeping the nation's roads safe. In this regard many lives that would have otherwise been wasted have been saved. The foregoing is, however, not suggesting that the F.R.S.C. had totally eradicated carnage on the nation's roads. Far be from it as daily reports show that accidents on roads are still as constant as the northern star.

Ofoji (2012) while examining the causes of accidents submits that most accidents occur as a consequence of bad driving. On the surface, this tends to absolve the F.R.S.C. of any blame when accidents occur. But taking a closer look at this problem, the F.R.S.C. cannot be exempted from blame since it is generally expected to prevent accidents on the roads. All causes of accident should therefore be eliminated or minimized including bad driving.

The F.R.S.C. is also expected to make the highways safe for motorists, and in this respect, the desired result had not been achieved. The hydra-headed problem of making highways safe involves other agencies of government like the Federal Ministry of Power, Works and Housing, Police, Vehicle Inspection Officers (V.I.O.) among others. If there is any laxity in this respect, the shortcomings are equally shared by other relevant agencies for their lackadaisical attitude and singling the F.R.S.C. for blame is thus out of the question.

Obaro (2015) opines that the F.R.S.C. had not satisfactorily carried out its responsibility of preventing obstructions on roads. The fact that many vehicles were abandoned had been a major setback in the quest to achieving safety on the roads. Vehicles spoilt or otherwise, littered the nation's highways without fear of being arrested or sanctioned by the F.R.S.C. The impunity by which this continues had assumed an alarming rate and the F.R.S.C. appeared powerless in this regard to carry out its mandate.

In examining the effectiveness or otherwise of the F.R.S.C. in carrying out its mandate, it would be quite pertinent to examine the issue in the global perspective of law enforcement generally in the country. While Nigerians have a penchant for disobeying the law on the one hand, the enforcement agencies are most often than not hamstrung, in - capacitated or simply incapable of enforcing the law. Just like other government agencies, the F.R.S.C. is bedeviled by several factors militating against its readiness to combat crime and thus prevent accidents on the nation's highways.

In order to understand the foregoing well, it is quite pertinent to consider the fact that other law enforcement agencies in Nigeria carry firearms, and even in the face of this, criminals and criminality thrive to a large extent. One would now want to imagine the attitude of miscreants to the F.R.S.C. who is not armed in the discharge of its responsibilities. In other climes, the mere presence of uniformed officers and men is enough to prevent crime and enforce the law but unfortunately the reverse is the case in Nigeria.

The foregoing suggests that the F.R.S.C. had been a total failure in the discharge of its mandate of ensuring safety on the roads. One interesting thing to observe here is that the F.R.S.C is certainly disadvantaged in any assessment of its activities. If and when accidents occur, the blame is on the Commission because statistics of accidents are readily available and noticeable. The problem here is that if accidents are prevented, statistics are not available to the credit of the F.R.S.C. The presence of the men and officers of the Commission at dangerous bends and hills on highways, for instance, have been known to prevent accidents but statistics would not be able to capture this or if a driver is booked for over - speeding or drunk - driving or dangerous overtaking and such a driver mends his ways and is thus prevented from wasting his life and those of others, the F.R.S.C cannot be applauded because such a fact is lost to statistics.

The F.R.S.C and relevant agencies

As it had been pointed out elsewhere in this paper, the F.R.S.C is not alone in enforcing safety on Nigerian roads. There are other sister agencies whose mandate is similar to those of the Commission. These, most often than not, work at cross - purposes and thus hamper the task of the F.R.S.C.

Chidoka (2012) identifies some of such sister agencies as the Federal Ministry of Environment. The F.R.S.C and this Ministry collaborate to check excessive automobile emissions. These are harmful to both animals and plants. The F.R.S.C also collaborates with the Federal Bureau of Statistics. The F.R.S.C supplies data to the Bureau for research purposes and national developmental plans (Chidoka, 2012).

It is also pertinent to observe that the F.R.S.C also works with the Nigeria Police Force (N.P.F) in the area of data sharing on road accidents and recovery of stolen vehicles (Chidoka, 2012). The relationship between the F.R.S.C and the N.P.F was rather a precarious one. Between 1999 and 2003, the F.R.S.C was under the supervision of the N.P.F (Federal Road Safety Corps, 2009). Even with the de-merger in 2003, the relationship was not cordial. The N.P.F had its Traffic Division which was always working at cross - purposes with the F.R.S.C.

Yet another area where frosty relations existed between the F.R.S.C and another sister agency is with the Vehicle Inspection Office (V.I.O). In a declaration, Mr. Boboye Oyeyemi, the Corps Marshall of the F.R.S.C opines that the V.I.O. should not inspect vehicles and ask for drivers' licenses as these were statutory functions of the F.R.S.C. Debunking this, Rev. Bayo Oluyemi asserts that the V.I.O. were adequately empowered to inspect vehicles and ask for drivers' licenses. The mutual rivalry seemed unending.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper examined a history of the F.R.S.C between 1988 and 2016. The F.R.S.C was the first attempt by successive Nigerian leaders to establish a uniform road safety policy for the whole country since independence. Hitherto there had been attempts aimed at ensuring safety on the nation's roads but they were limited by lack of commitment and sincerity of purpose.

To address this yawning gap, therefore, the F.R.S.C was established by law. A close examination has revealed that Nigerians has a penchant for exotic cars, the purchase of which came readily as a result of the oil boom. The resultant effect of the foregoing is a rapid increase in the number of vehicles on the roads.

However, there is a noticeable decrease in the quality of highways in Nigeria partly due to neglect, corruption, insecurity, political instability, economic recession and so on. The foregoing meant a new pressure on the F.R.S.C if it was to maintain safety on the highways. To compound the problem, the Commission is not adequately staffed to effectively monitor the nation's highways. There is also an acute dearth of materials and resources.

In spite of this gloomy picture, however, it was observed that the F.R.S.C was doing its best, within available resources to ensure safety on the roads. In this regard, statistics are not readily

available to buttress the fact that the F.R.S.C was up to the task of securing and maintaining safety on the roads.

To strengthen and further empower the F.R.S.C, the following recommendations are submitted:

The F.R.S.C should be a truly independent organization that is empowered by law to function as such. The National Assembly is called upon to review the necessary instruments establishing the F.R.S.C with a view to making it more relevant and better equipped to cope with present day challenges.

Secondly, the F.R.S.C should be further empowered through better funding. Without adequate funding, the F.R.S.C., like any other organization cannot function effectively.

Thirdly, the Federal Government should introduce the use of firearms to the F.R.S.C to make miscreants and road users fear and respect it. For a start, this could be done on a limited scale and with proper training; the use of firearms could be extended to all cadres of staff.

Moreover, there should be synergy between all sister agencies to ensure safety on the roads. Since the ultimate goal is to ensure safety on the roads and thus stimulate national development, all hands must be on deck to achieve this. The era when government agencies and parastatals with similar aims and objectives work at cross - purposes should be over.

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